

Approaches towards a cost effective practical method of removal of arsenic from contaminated groundwater

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Abstract : This article describes one removal option for procuring groundwater for domestic purpose, which becomes free from arsenic. Synthesis of crystalline hydrous ferric oxide (CHFO) having arsenic removal capacity has already been reported. Ganga sand, which is rich in iron can remove As^{III} from aqueous solution has also been reported. In this study a mixture of CHFO and Ganga sand in definite proportions have been tried to see their efficiency in removing both As^{III} and As^V. The analysis of preliminary results show that this method can bring down arsenic level in contaminated groundwater from 1.0 mg/L to 0.026 mg/L. By conducting batch and column studies the effect of pH, contact time, initial adsorbate concentration and adsorption criteria were studied.

Keywords : Crystalline ferric oxide, Ganga sand, adsorption, arsenic removal, batch study, column test.

Introduction

Contamination of arsenic in groundwater is one of the major environmental problems and is considered a global issue. As a naturally occurring toxic substance in the earth's crust, arsenic enters into aquifers and wells through natural processes and to the water cycle as a result of anthropogenic activities. The occurrence of geogenic As^{III} and As^V is a severe problem particularly in Bangladesh and West Bengal in India where a large population is seriously affected due to high concentration of arsenic in groundwater which is higher than maximum contaminated level (0.01 mg/L) as prescribed by WHO.

Arsenic occurs in groundwater as As^{III} and As^V of which As^{III} is more toxic and difficult to remove. As^{III} existing as H₃AsO₃ is a hydrophilic, neutral species below pH 9.0 and is not accessible to the major removal processes involving sorption and anion exchange. For oxidation of As^{III} to As^V in groundwater, a mild selective oxidizing agent is needed. Oxidizing agents used for this purpose include MnO₂¹, ozone². Residual concentration of these oxidizing agents may have toxic effects on human health and should be treated properly.

Several studies have demonstrated that arsenic removal

can be achieved by various technologies. They include lime treatment, co-precipitation, adsorption onto coagulated flocs, adsorption onto sorptive media, usage of ion exchange resins, membranes and reverse osmosis. As proposed by USEPA (United State Environmental Protection Agency) adsorption methods have been successfully applied for high efficiency removal of arsenic from groundwater. Adsorption media widely used are activated alumina³, ion exchange resins, iron based compounds, silica sand etc. Ferrihydrite⁴, amorphous iron oxide⁵, granular ferric hydroxide⁶, iron oxide coated sand⁷, hydrated zirconium oxide⁸ and titanium oxide⁹, lanthanum¹⁰ and yttrium carbonates¹¹ as adsorption media have been studied in details by different authors.

Synthesis of one modified iron based compound e.g. crystalline hydrous ferric oxide (CHFO), which has arsenic removal capacity and avoids recycling into environment has been reported by Manna *et al.*¹². Ganga sand has As^{III} removal capacity and that has been investigated by Vaisya and Agarwal¹³.

The objective of the present study is to evaluate the potential and applicability of a mixture of CHFO and Ganga sand for removing both species of As from ground-

water. This method has been tried because the method appears to be cost-effective, easy to operate and user friendly.

Results and discussion

For CHFO it has been observed from batch sorption studies performed at room temperature that the percent removal of As^{III} and As^V from their respective solutions are dependent on their concentration and pH. For arsenic concentration ranging from 5 to 15 mg/L, the percentage adsorption of both the species remain the same up to a pH of 6.2. At pH > 6.2, arsenic(V) adsorption decreases but As^{III} adsorption remains the same and decreases above pH 9.0. Increase of arsenic concentration above 60 mg/L and above has decreasing effect on As^V adsorption above a pH of 2.8, but has no effect on arsenic(III) up to a pH of 9.0. It appears that for As^V, removal efficiency is controlled by both concentration and pH while that for As^{III} is independent of concentration for pH ≤ 9.0.

In case of As^{III} adsorption by Ganga sand it was observed that the adsorption capacity attains a maximum value between pH 7–9 followed by a decrease in the range 9–12. Maximum optimal pH was 7.6. For arsenic(V), maximum adsorption occurred at pH 6.4. The effect of pH can be understood from the predominance diagram of ionic species of arsenic by Smith and Martell¹⁴.

Fig. 1. Predominance diagram for As^{III} and As^V as a function of pH.

In case of As^{III} keeping the initial adsorbate dose constant and increasing the adsorbent dose, it was observed that unit adsorption decreased. This decrease in unit adsorption was described as “solid concentration effect” by Honeyman and Santschy¹⁵.

Possible explanations for pH effect :

As^V exist as H₂AsO₄⁻ and HAsO₄²⁻ in solution as

dominating species in the pH range 3–6 and 8–11 respectively. The arsenite species are H₃AsO₃, H₂AsO₃⁻ and HAsO₃²⁻ existing predominantly in the pH range upto 9.0, greater than 9.0 and above 12.0.

The percentage of arsenic species was calculated using the pK_a values of arsenate and arsenite species (pK_a^I, pK_a^{II}, pK_a^{III} of H₃AsO₄ are 2.19, 6.94 and 11.5 respectively. pK_a^I of H₃AsO₃ is 9.21).

Oxyanionic species of arsenic adsorb at oxyhydroxide surface by forming complexes with the surface sites as proposed by Edwards¹⁶. The adsorption is specific which may involve the replacement of surface hydroxyl group by the adsorbing ligand. An electrostatic interaction may occur as well.

As^{III} adsorption may take place due to ion-dipole type of interaction.

The effect of pH in case of Ganga sand can be interpreted with the structure of the sorbent and ionic species diagram of H₃AsO₄ and H₃AsO₃. The major constituent of Ganga sand is SiO₂. The three dimensional structure of SiO₂ may be described as being composed of SiO₂ tetrahedra, in which each oxygen atom is shared between two adjacent tetrahedra. The Si–O bond is polar and tends to accumulate cations e.g. H⁺ present in aqueous medium. The accumulation of H⁺ makes the surface positively charged. The positively charged surface then adsorbs H₂AsO₄⁻ in lower pH range. There is less adsorption of As^{III} in the pH range 3–7 due to presence of neutral H₃AsO₃. In the pH range 7–9, H₂AsO₃⁻ is the predominant species due to dissociation of weak H₃AsO₃ and is likely to be adsorbed. As pH increases above 9.0, the amount of negatively charged arsenic species rises, while the number of positively charged surface sites decreases.

The non-availability of (+)ve charges on the adsorbent surface is not favourable for adsorption of (-)vely charged ions.

Effect of contact time :

The effect of contact time between a definite amount of CHFO and different concentrations of As^{III} and As^V were conducted at pH 6.4 in batch experiment. The time of agitation was between one to eight hours. For a definite concentration of arsenic with a definite adsorbent dose, it was observed that the percentage adsorption of As^{III} required less contact time. The equilibrium time for maximum adsorption was independent of concentration, the contact time for maximum adsorption was 3.5 h and 5.6 h for As^{III} and As^V respectively. This is also supported by the experimental studies of Manna *et al.*¹².

Fig. 2. Plot of percent adsorption of As^{III} and As^V with time in case of CHFO. Initial concentration of As^{III} and As^V = 50 mg/L, sorbent dose = 0.2 g/50 ml. (○) indicates As^{III}, (Δ) indicates As^V.

In case of Ganga sand for a fixed mass of the adsorbent, having definite initial concentration of As^{III} and As^V, the maximum adsorption took place between 3 to 4 h in case of As^{III}. For As^V maximum adsorption took place at 5 h. The equilibrium time was almost 8 h.

Fig. 3. Plot of percent adsorption of As^{III} with time in case of Ganga sand. Initial concentration of As^{III} = 1.0 mg/L, sorbent dose = 10 g/L.

Fig. 4. Plot of percent adsorption of As^V with time in case of Ganga sand. Initial concentration of As^V = 1.0 mg/L, sorbent dose = 10 g/L.

Adsorption isotherms :

The adsorption equilibrium data were obtained in the pH range 6.8–7.2. Adsorption isotherm using Langmuir’s model was applied in this connection. The linear form of Langmuir isotherm can be represented as

$$q_e = bq_m C_e / (1 + bC_e)$$

$$1/q_e = 1/bq_m \cdot 1/C_e + 1/q_m$$

q_e is the mass of arsenic adsorbed per unit mass of the adsorbent (mg/g), C_e is the equilibrium concentration (mg/L). The constant b and q_m are related to equilibrium adsorption constant and adsorption capacity.

The linear nature of the plot is indicative of following Langmuir’s isotherm. It suggests monolayer coverage of sorbate at the outer surface of the adsorbent.

Figs. 5 and 6 show the plots of Langmuir’s isotherm for CHFO and Ganga sand.

Fig. 5. Plot of Langmuir adsorption isotherm of As^{III} and As^V adsorption on CHFO. Initial concentration of As^{III} and As^V = 25 mg/L, sorbent dose = 0.2 g/50 ml. (○) indicates As^V, (Δ) indicates As^{III}.

Fig. 6. Plot of Langmuir isotherm for As^{III} and As^V adsorption on Ganga sand. Initial concentration of As^{III} and As^V = 1.6 mg/L, sorbent dose = 2 g/50 ml. (□) indicates As^{III}, (○) indicates As^V.

Column studies :

In the laboratory a down flow column test was performed using a mixture of crystalline hydrous ferric oxide and Ganga sand. The particle size was (0.17–0.3) mm for CHFO and (0.24–0.28) mm for Ganga sand. A glass column of height about 375 mm and internal diameter 15 mm was used. The bed height was 15 cm. The substances were mixed in definite proportions and the mass of CHFO and Ganga sand required for the purpose was calculated. The arsenic bearing water was groundwater spiked with 1.0 mg/L of As^{III} using sodium arsenite and 1.0 mg/L of As^V using sodium arsenate. The flow rate was 2 ml/min. The empty bed contact time was 10.2 min for both the samples. After the first two cycles were run upto exhaustion, As^{III} and As^V yielded value of 0.024 mg/L for As^{III} and 0.027 mg/L for As^V. Although the value is little above the maximum contaminated level prescribed by WHO, it indicates that CHFO along with Ganga sand have removal capacities of arsenic from ground water. The medium was generated using (N) NaOH solution followed by backwashing with double distilled water.

Experimental

Glasswares : All glasswares and sample bottles having Brandname 'Borosil' were washed with detergent solution, rinsed with tap water, soaked in 8 M HNO₃ for atleast twelve hours and finally rinsed with distilled water.

Chemicals : All the chemicals used were of analytical

grade and were used without purification. The As^{III} stock solution was prepared from arsenious oxide and As^V solution was prepared from disodium hydrogen arsenate heptahydrate (Na₂HAsO₄·7H₂O). In both cases standard stock solutions (1000 mg/L) were prepared and preserved. All other chemicals were of analytical reagent grade.

Water : Through out the experiment double distilled water was used.

Synthesis of the adsorbent CHFO : A crystalline form of hydrous ferric oxide was prepared from 0.1 M FeCl₃ solution in 0.01 M HCl. Concentrated NH₃ solution was added in calculated amount followed by 0.1 M NH₄OH solution added drop by drop, by constant stirring when brown ferric hydroxide was precipitated. The pH of the solution was maintained between 4.5–5.0. The brown precipitate was aged with the mother liquor for four days. The supernatant liquid was decanted.

The precipitate was washed with water until free from acid. The precipitate was filtered and dried in air oven at 50 °C. The Ganga sand was collected from the river Ganga near Barrackpore belt, North 24-Parganas, West Bengal. The sand was washed with distilled water, dried in sun and finally in an air oven at 110 °C.

Analysis of arsenic in water sample : Arsenic determination was done by generating AsH₃ in a Gutzeit generator using silver diethyl dithio carbamate (SDDC), prescribed by standard methods. Arsenic analysis was performed spectrophotometrically using Systronic spectrophotometer (Model visiscan-167). A calibration curve was drawn ($\lambda_{\max} = 520 \text{ nm}$).

Sorption experiments with CHFO and Ganga sand :

Batch sorption experiments were performed at room temperature (32 ± 2) °C. Shaking was done in a mechanical shaker at 85 rpm. 50 ml of aliquot of different concentration were prepared from stock solution. Each set of solution was treated with 0.2 g of CHFO and 5 g of Ganga sand as the case may be. The pH of the solution were measured before and after experiment. pH of test solution and adsorbent were adjusted using 0.1 N NaOH or 0.2 N HCl.

After removing the bottles from the shaker when equilibrium has been attained, the solutions were filtered and filtrate were analysed for arsenic using SDDC method.

Conclusions :

Within the limited scope and short span of time it has not been possible to study several factors which are relevant in improving the adsorption capacity. Further investigations are required. Nevertheless, the results obtained so far clearly demonstrate that the selected adsorbents can be used as a filter media in a domestic water purifier for arsenic. CHFO has moderately high adsorption capacity (0.06 mg/g) for As^{III} and (0.052 mg/g) for As^V. Although Ganga sand has low capacity almost (0.026 mg/g) for As^{III} and As^V, still it is used in conjunction with CHFO as a low cost adsorbent. The method is simple and causes no adverse health effects.

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